

**THE SOCIAL IMPORTANCE OF HIGHER EDUCATION
VIRTUALISATION**

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Abstract: *In this article, the importance of higher education development in improving the quality of education, as well as the philosophical content of the concept of education is revealed. Analytical information on the development of virtual and online education has been provided in the informed society.*

Key words: *higher education, learning, virtual education, online education, quality of Education, cognition, scientific information.*

Today, the most important institutions of society are losing their material "emotionality", predictability and moving to the form of electronic digital media communication. For the traditional consciousness, the concept of "university" is primarily associated with the concept of a complex of buildings (a student's town), classrooms filled with students led by professors. Everything is presented in a clear material shell and, of course, in a fully Real available mode. This stereotype of perception of the university is manifested in the fact that it is now necessary to give up. The university remains a complex adaptive system of digital information transmission and management. The university is gradually and partially becoming "virtual", that is, the process of training does not require the passage of physical distances, the full time of its subjects, but in most cases the involvement of all participants in the same space and at the same time is not required.

Communication relations in the university environment are moving to new qualities - online infocommunication. This process is objective. It simply does not chase the trend of innovation. On the contrary, this trend significantly increases the effectiveness of educational activities and creates fundamentally new horizons of Education.

Higher School of Economics headed by Professor N.E.The Pokrovsky a group of young scientists working in general sociology conduct research in order to study, model and test the process of university and scientific communications in the

modern world. Each of the materials they bring touches on this or that aspect of virtualizing the educational process in a modern university. Some aspects are self-evident, for example, the extensive computerization and digitization of instructional materials, the use of visual tools for the presentation of texts and additional lectures. Events such as the continuation of communication between the reader and the teacher on educational issues, the transfer to the Internet environment are becoming increasingly common. However, more radical innovations are associated with the development of distance learning in the format of online teleconference and satellite broadcasting. The program is dedicated to the research of these phenomena, the result of which is presented in publications.

The rapid development of the next communication technologies of the XX-XXI century caused quality changes in society. The term "Virtual reality" has become a symbol of the modern era. Virtually implies the construction of simulation structures in all spheres of society, both in economics, politics, education, and in the presence of a wide range of opportunities for simulation. In the literature, the term "virtual worlds" is often will show, which defines areas of special symbolic and social concentration. They consist of simulations and often do not have a strong connection with the reference of substance.

In the modern sense, nobility was introduced into the discussion in the 70-80-ies of the last century. In the article "simulators and simulations", Jean Baudrillard presents the concept of "simulacrum", which is considered basic. He considers the process of "development" of the character or sign from a simple link to the referent to the "view without originals", the infinite distribution of its own copies, which has nothing to do with reality; this process brings out a new state of reality called "hyperreality".¹⁵

The concept of Virtual University is interpreted very differently in at least two research traditions. Thus, within the framework of one of these traditions, it is spoken about the simulation of educational and scientific practices of the University. Academic status becomes a function of the image of powers that are worthy of funding. More time and effort will be spent on creating and presenting the image necessary to succeed in competitions for grants in the activities of scientists and students, scholarships for study abroad, orders for consulting services, etc. Therefore, in recent decades, social technologies have developed that are suitable for the simulation of competence: research funds, grants, consulting, conferences, academic exchanges, continuous education.¹⁶

¹⁵ Baudrillard, Jean. (1981) *Simulacra and Simulations* // Baudrillard, Jean (1988) *Jean Baudrillard. Selected Writings*.

¹⁶ Ivanov D.V. *Virtualization of society*. St. Petersburg: "Petersburg Oriental Studies", 2000. - 96 p.

With the substitution of material objects and Real actions with simulacras, the performance of the social roles of the scientist, teacher and student becomes virtual. As a result, the hierarchy of scientific degrees and titles (academic community), scientific discussions (conferences, competitions), the division of scientific labor (research, educational organization), that is, the University and the scientific laboratory are represented as social institutions. At the same time, in another tradition, the terms virtual University or virtual Education indicate that the educational process is carried out through the mediation of technology, which leads to a different perception of space and time.¹⁷ In subsequent studies, it is accepted that the term is understood exactly this way. Today, almost every university has created opportunities for experiments in the field of virtual education. While some are motivated by the desire to improve the quality of Education, others are trying to find new ways to save money and attract additional students. Virtual University and virtual education in a broader context implies the transfer of knowledge with the use of some technical means, for example, the Internet and other information telecommunications.

Students and teachers do not interact at a single geographic point, their connection is divided into space (and sometimes time) and provides a horde with technical means. The most common types of University educationualualization are technologicalualualization, the process of learning is carried out by technological systems such as online distance learning platforms, multimedia and other forms of information and communication technologies; with geographic virtualization, the audience of students is distributed to large areas and never (or almost never) meet in one place. It is important to evaluate the different models of virtual universities in order to understand which strategies are Real, stable and successful, what will turn out to be the most important and valuable for students and teachers, under what conditions these models can be successfully implemented. The use of technology as an intermediary between students and teachers is not new. However, the complexity, diversity and ubiquitous availability of a technological learning environment form a new approach to traditional understanding of what education is actually. Let's look at the main forms of ualualizasiya in the field of university education.

Classical distance learning. Forms of distance learning appeared long before the creation of the Internet. Students were provided with educational tools (textbooks, Readers, video recordings of lectures, software), which allowed them to

¹⁷ Willoughby, Kelvin W. (2003) The Virtualization of University Education: Concepts, Strategies and Business Models. Discussion Paper #75, September 15-19, 2003. <http://it.coe.uga.edu/itforum/paper75/paper75.html>

formulate the learning process at a distance. However, this form of education was recently around university life. The emergence of broadband data transmission channels has changed the situation to the better side. Videoconference communication systems made it possible to organize direct interaction between students and teachers in the form of interactive audiovisual communication. It became technologically possible to conduct lectures, seminars and other training sessions in several places at the same time. Interactive web learning a number of universities (for example, the University of British Columbia in Canada, Duke University in North Carolina, USA, etc.) are implementing their own web platforms, which allowed them to create a full virtual learning environment that is available 24 hours a day, 7 days a week. One of the most successful examples of this model was the full virtual The New School University in New York. Full virtual courses for the student, a discussion area, services designed to communicate with teachers (tips, examinations, etc.k.) was invited. At the same time, the interaction environment can be simulated, for example, by involving the technologies of popular three-dimensional online games.¹⁸

In the minds of many faculties, kafed kafed yo'qligi bildiradi, jismon yo'qligi yo'qligi lack of university infrastructure actually means that the university does not exist. Thus, the question of the possibility of virtualizing education goes to another level, and "can there be a virtual academic environment and a virtual university community?"it has become customary to be expressed as such. Given the success of the experiments (for example, the campus mentioned in SecondLife, or virtual The New School University), it is possible to achieve virtualization of the university environment.

¹⁸ Johnson, Laurence F.; Levine, Alan H. (2008) Virtual Worlds: Inherently Immersive, Highly Social Learning Spaces. Theory Into Practice, 47:161–170, 2008.

